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A revision on Multi-Criteria Decision Making methods for Multi-UAV Mission Planning Support

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Abstract

Over the last decade, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have been extensively used in many commercial applications due to their manageability and risk avoidance. One of the main problems considered is the Mission Planning for multiple UAVs, where a solution plan must be found satisfying the different constraints of the problem. Moreover, this problem has some variables that must be optimized simultaneously, such as the makespan, the cost of the mission or the risk. Due to this, the problem has a lot of possible optimal solutions, and the operator must select the final solution to be executed among them. In order to reduce the workload of the operator in this decision process, a Decision Support System (DSS) becomes necessary. In this work, a DSS consisting of ranking and filtering functions, which order and reduce the optimal solutions, has been designed. A wide range of Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) methods, including some fuzzy MCDM, are compared on a multi-UAV mission planning scenario, in order to study which method could fit better in a multi-UAV decision support system. Expert operators have evaluated the solutions returned in order to score and compare fuzzy-based methods against classical ones, and the results show that fuzzy methods generally achieve better average scores. On the other hand, for the filtering system, a similarity function based on the proximity of the solutions has been designed, and the threshold used for the filtering is studied.

Keywords: Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, Mission Planning, Multi-Criteria Decision Making, Fuzzy methods

1. Introduction

2 The fast development of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) capabilities in
3 the last years has led to an upswing in new military and commercial applications,

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4 where many fields such as surveillance (Gu et al., 2018), training (Rodriguez-
5 Fernandez et al., 2018), fire fighting (Ghamry et al., 2017), agriculture (Tokekar
6 et al., 2016) or disaster and crisis management (Nedjati et al., 2016) have been
7 researched.

8 One of the main research fields of UAVs is mission planing, where a col-
9 laborative swarm of UAVs must perform some tasks taking into account some
10 spatial and time constraints. It is a highlight goal in UAV research, since it is a
11 complex problem that hardens UAV operators workload. Nowadays, UAVs are
12 controlled remotely by human operators from Ground Control Stations (GCSs),
13 using rudimentary planning systems, such as pre-configured plans, manually
14 provided schedules or classical planners. These classical planners, based on a
15 graph search or a logic engine, usually undergo severe practical limitations and
16 their solvers have a high computational cost.

17 In order to undertake complex coordinated missions, planning systems dem-
18 and more efficient problem-solving capabilities to cope with conflicting objec-
19 tives and stringent constraints over both spatial and time domains. In addition,
20 these problems usually aim to optimize several conflicting objectives, including
21 the fuel consumption, the makespan, the cost of the mission, the number of
22 UAVs to employ and different risk factors that could compromise the mission,
23 among others. Therefore, the so-called Multi-UAV Cooperative Mission Plan-
24 ning Problem (MCMPP) have lately gained momentum in the research commu-
25 nity, propelled by a notable increase in the scales and number of applications
26 foreseen for UAVs in the near future (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2017b).

27 Nowadays, in most GCSs, there are several operators that usually deal with
28 just one UAV, due to the high complexity of a mission. One of the main aims
29 in this field is to reduce this complexity, so this relation can be swapped, and
30 in a near future a single operator would control multiple vehicles. For this,
31 one of the principal requirements is to automatize and reduce the complex-
32 ity of the MCMPP. In previous works, the MCMPP has been formulated as a
33 Constraint Satisfaction Problem (CSP) (Ramirez-Atencia & Camacho, 2018a).
34 In that work, the variables of the problem are the assignments of UAVs to
35 tasks, GCSs, sensors and further variables, and several spatial and tempo-
36 ral constraints are defined to assure the consistency of the solutions. Then,
37 the problem has been solved using a Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm
38 (MOEA) (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2018a), considering seven conflicting objec-
39 tives. In this algorithm, an estimation of the Pareto Optimal Frontier (POF)
40 is inferred so as to get a portfolio of solutions (mission plans) differently albeit
41 optimally balancing the considered conflicting objectives.

42 One critical point in this problem, and the motivation of this work, is that
43 sometimes the entire POF comprises a large number of solutions. In this situa-
44 tion, the process of decision making to select one solution among them becomes
45 a difficult task for the operator. In some cases, the operator can provide a priori
46 information about his/her preferences, which can be used in the optimization
47 process. However, most times the operator does not provide this information,
48 so a posteriori approaches must be considered. In this case, the a posteriori
49 multi-objective optimization algorithm will most times return a large number

50 of solutions, and the decision process becomes highly complex.

51 Such was the case in (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2018a), where a large number
52 of non-dominated solutions were obtained. In order to reduce the number of
53 solutions, in (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2017a), a Knee-Point MOEA approach
54 was used to only return the most significant ones according to the optimization
55 variables, i.e. the knee points of the POF. Although this approach highly reduces
56 the number of solutions (from hundreds to tens), in most cases there will still be
57 several solutions and the operator has to take the final decision of which one is
58 the most appropriate for the mission. This decision process is not easy, as each
59 solution comprises several variable assignments and several criteria defining its
60 quality.

61 In this context, a Decision Support System (DSS) becomes essential for guid-
62 ing the operator in the process of selecting the best solution. This DSS provides
63 a ranking system that will order the solutions obtained by the optimization
64 algorithm, and, additionally, a filtering system that reduces the number of solu-
65 tions provided. There exists several Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM)
66 methods that can be used to rank and select the solutions based on the oper-
67 ator preferences, which are used as percentages of importance or orders of the
68 different criteria. Nevertheless, sometimes these preferences may be fuzzy, so
69 they must be considered in a different way. For these cases, there exist fuzzy
70 versions of the MCDM methods, where these preferences are treated as fuzzy
71 numbers.

72 The goal of this paper is to develop a DSS to assist UAV operators in the
73 selection of the mission plan. In a previous work (Ramirez-Atencia et al.,
74 2018b), some classical MCDM methods where used to rank the solutions of
75 the MCMPP returned by a MOEA (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2017a). In this
76 paper, new MCDM methods are considered, as well as their fuzzy versions. As
77 the preferences provided by operators are also fuzzy, it is expected for these
78 methods to provide better results. A number of realistic mission scenarios is
79 used to test these methods. Expert operators evaluated the solutions provided
80 for each mission according to some operator profiles (preferences), and through
81 this evaluation, the MCDM algorithms have been scored. In addition, a filter-
82 ing system that omits similar solutions has been designed and tested in order
83 to provide a complete Multi-Criteria DSS.

84 The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents some back-
85 ground on DSS, including Fuzzy MCDM. Section 3 describes the UAV mission
86 planning problem and the DSS developed to help the operator in the selection
87 of the best solutions, including the ranking and filtering systems. Section 4
88 presents the results obtained in the experiments for both the ranking and fil-
89 tering systems. Finally, the last section draws conclusions and outlines future
90 research lines related to this work.

91 2. Background on Decision Support Systems

92 DSSs (Shim et al., 2002; Fülöp, 2005) are information systems used in deci-
93 sion making and problem solving. Research on DSS is focused on the efficiency

94 of user decision making and how to increase the effectiveness of that decision.
 95 One of the most common fields in DSS is MCDM (Triantaphyllou, 2000), where
 96 multiple criteria $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n \in F$ are taken into account for each of the alter-
 97 natives $s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m \in S$ considered. The problems of MCDM appear and are
 98 intensely applied in many domains, such as Economics, Social Sciences, Medical
 99 Sciences etc.

100 There are two main subfields in MCDM: Multi-Objective Decision Making
 101 (MODM), focused on design problems, and Multi-Attribute Decision Making
 102 (MADM), focused on evaluation problems. In MODM alternatives are not ex-
 103 plicitly known, but instead a mathematical model is used to find them. In most
 104 cases, there is an infinite or very large number of alternatives, and the methods
 105 in this subfield are mostly the same as in Multi-Objective Optimization.

106 On the other hand, in MADM (Triantaphyllou & Shu, 2001), there is a finite
 107 number of alternatives, represented by their performance in multiple (conflict-
 108 ing) criteria. The decision makers have to provide some weights or preferences
 109 for each of these criteria (e.g. percentage numbers, degrees of importance, etc.).
 110 The main goals in these problems are choice, sorting or ranking (Zavadskas
 111 et al., 2006). In choice problems, one or a few incomparable alternatives are
 112 selected as the best alternative. In sorting problems, alternatives are grouped
 113 into predefined categories, with similar behaviors or characteristics. In ranking
 114 problems, alternatives are ordered from best to worst according to some scores
 115 or pairwise comparisons. For this last kind of problems, there exist several
 116 methods, such as the following:

- 117 • **Weighted Sum Model (WSM)** (Triantaphyllou, 2000). This approach
 118 consists of an utility function with weight values w_f (in the interval $[0, 1]$)
 119 for each criteria or factor $f \in F$, according to their importance. Given the
 120 values $v_f(s)$ for each factor in an alternative or solution $s \in S$, the utility
 121 function for WSM can be expressed as a weighted sum:

$$rank_{value}(s) = \sum_{f \in F} \frac{w_f \times v_f(s)}{\max_{s' \in S} v_f(s')} \quad (1)$$

122 All of these $rank_{value}(s)$ are then used to rank the alternatives.

- 123 • **Weighted Product Model (WPM)** (Tofallis, 2014). This method is
 124 similar to WSM, but instead of addition, each decision alternative is com-
 125 pared with the others by multiplying a number of ratios, one for each
 126 decision criterion. Each ratio is raised to the power equivalent to the
 127 relative weight of the corresponding criterion. In order to compare two
 128 solutions s_i and s_j , whose criteria values are $v_f(s_i)$ and $v_f(s_j)$, then the
 129 following product is considered:

$$P^{(s_i/s_j)} = \prod_{f \in F} \left(\frac{v_f(s_i)}{v_f(s_j)} \right)^{w_f} \quad (2)$$

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where the ratio $P(s_i/s_j) \geq 1$ indicates that alternative s_i is better.

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- **Analytic Hierarchic Process (AHP)** (Saaty, 2001). This method allows individuals or groups to make complex decisions. The procedure of AHP firstly decomposes the decision problem into a hierarchy of more easily comprehended sub-problems, and then analyse each of them independently, comparing each pair of elements of the hierarchy. In most problems, there would be three levels in this hierarchy, in the following top-down order: the goal, the criteria and the alternatives. The core concept of AHP is that alternatives are always compared pairwise. For this, the decision makers must provide the weights as pairwise comparisons of the criteria (e.g. using a scale 1-9 where 1 means equally important and 9 means the first is extremely important compared to the second), resulting in a matrix A of weight comparisons. Also, for each criteria, alternatives are similarly compared pairwise according to that criterion.

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All of these comparisons are converted to numerical values, providing a numerical weight or priority for each element of the hierarchy. Several methods can be used in this process (e.g. approximation method, geometric mean, etc.), being the Eigenvalue method the most common. In this method, the priorities p of each alternative/criteria are computed as the eigenvectors of the following equation:

$$A \cdot p = \lambda \cdot p \quad (3)$$

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where λ is the eigenvalue, i.e. the maximum value satisfying the equation. Then, based on these priorities on each level of the hierarchy, numerical priorities can be calculated for each of the decision alternatives through additive aggregation (or in some cases multiplicative aggregation):

$$P_s = \sum_{f \in F} w_f \cdot p_{sf} \quad (4)$$

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where P_s is the global priority of alternative s , w_f is the priority of criterion f and p_{sf} is the priority of alternative s w.r.t criterion f . Based on these global priorities, alternatives are ranked.

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- **VIKOR** (Opricovic & Tzeng, 2004). This method solves decision problems with conflicting and noncommensurable (different units) criteria. Assuming that compromise is acceptable for conflict resolution, the decision maker looks for a compromise solution F^C that is the closest to the ideal F^* , and the alternatives are evaluated according to all established criteria. In its process, VIKOR determines the best f^* and the worst f^- values for every criteria $f \in F$. Then, the weighted and normalized Manhattan (S_s) and Chebyshev (R_s) distances are computed for every alternative:

$$S_s = \sum_{f \in F} \frac{w_f \cdot (f^* - v_f(s))}{f^* - f^-} \quad (5)$$

$$R_s = \max_{f \in F} \frac{w_f \cdot (f^* - v_f(s))}{f^* - f^-} \quad (6)$$

165 From these distances, the best $S^* = \min_k S_k$, $R^* = \min_k R_k$ and worst
 166 $S^- = \max_k S_k$, $R^- = \max_k R_k$ values are used to compute the maximum
 167 group utility (or majority of the criteria):

$$Q_s = v \cdot \frac{S_s - S^*}{S^- - S^*} + (1 - v) \cdot \frac{R_s - R^*}{R^- - R^*} \quad (7)$$

168 where v is the weight of the strategy of the maximum group utility, which
 169 could be compromised by $v = 0.5$. Following the method, VIKOR rank
 170 the alternatives by sorting the values of S , R and Q and proposes a com-
 171 promise solution as the best value of Q given some conditions. For ranking
 172 problems, Q ranking can be used.

173 • **Technique for the Order of Prioritisation by Similarity to Ideal**
 174 **Solution (TOPSIS)** (García-Cascales & Lamata, 2012). It is a method
 175 of compensatory aggregation that compares a set of alternatives by iden-
 176 tifying weights for each criterion, normalising scores for each criterion and
 177 calculating the geometric distance between each alternative and the ideal
 178 alternative, which is the best score in each criterion. An assumption of
 179 TOPSIS is that the criteria are monotonically increasing or decreasing.
 180 The normalisation can be performed using different procedures, such as
 181 vectorial (distributive) normalisation:

$$r_{sf} = \frac{v_f(s)}{\sqrt{\sum_{s' \in S} v_f(s')^2}} \quad (8)$$

182 or linear transformation of maximum (also called ideal normalization):

$$r_{sf} = \begin{cases} \frac{v_f(s)}{\max_{s' \in S} v_f(s')} & \text{if criterion } f \text{ is maximized} \\ \frac{\min_{s' \in S} v_f(s')}{v_f(s)} & \text{if criterion } f \text{ is minimized} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

183 These normalized scores are then multiplied by the corresponding weights
 184 w_f , and compared against the ideal and anti-ideal solutions. Virtual ideal
 185 and anti-ideal solutions are constructed as the best and worst scores on
 186 each criterion, respectively. Then, distance to the ideal d_s^+ and anti-ideal
 187 d_s^- solutions are computed for each solution s using the Euclidean distance.
 188 Finally, the closeness ratio for each alternative is computed as:

$$C_s = \frac{d_s^-}{d_s^+ + d_s^-} \quad (10)$$

189 This closeness ratio establishes the ranking, where the highest value indi-
 190 cates the preferred alternative.

191 • **ELECTRE** (Roy, 1991). It is an outranking method that compares all
 192 feasible alternatives by pair building up some binary relations, crisp or
 193 fuzzy, and then exploit in appropriate way these relations in order to ob-
 194 tain final recommendations. It is commonly used when there are more
 195 than two criteria to avoid the compensation effect of weights. Several
 196 ELECTRE methods were proposed for different kinds of problems, being
 197 ELECTRE II, ELECTRE III and ELECTRE IV proposed for ranking
 198 problems. ELECTRE III consists of two phases: first it constructs one
 199 or several outranking relations, which aims at comparing in a comprehen-
 200 sive way the alternatives, and then an exploitation procedure elaborates
 201 preference order using these outranking relations. Criteria in ELECTRE
 202 III have four distinct sets of parameters: the criteria weights (w), and
 203 the indifference (q), the preference (p) and the veto (v) thresholds. These
 204 thresholds indicate the largest difference between the performance of al-
 205 ternatives w.r.t a given criterion such that they remain indifferent (q), one
 206 is preferred over the other (p) or the ‘discordant’ difference in favour of
 207 one option negates any possible outranking relationship indicated by other
 208 criteria (v).

209 The outranking relation ‘ a outranks b ’, meaning that a is at least as good
 210 as b , is defined through the outranking degree $S(a, b) \in [0, 1]$, where a value
 211 closer to 1 indicates a stronger assertion. This outranking degree $S(a, b)$ is
 212 computed by aggregating two perspectives: concordance degree (using the
 213 indifference and preference thresholds) and discordance degree (using the
 214 veto threshold). For every criterion, partial concordance degree $c_f(a, b)$
 215 is computed using indifference q_f and preference p_f thresholds through
 216 linear interpolation, where if alternatives b is indifferent or worse than a
 217 according to q_f , then $c_f(a, b) = 1$, while if b is preferred to a according
 218 to p_f , then $c_f(a, b) = 0$. Then, the global concordance degree $C(a, b)$
 219 is computed as a weighted sum of partial concordance degrees. Partial
 220 discordance degree $d_f(a, b)$ is computed using veto threshold v_f through
 221 linear interpolation, where if alternatives b is better than a according to
 222 v_f (i.e. strong disagreement with the assertion), then $d_f(a, b) = 1$, while
 223 if a is as least as good as b according to p_f (i.e. no reason to refute the
 224 assertion), then $d_f(a, b) = 0$. Then, the outranking degree is computed
 225 using the concordance and discordance degrees as:

$$S(a, b) = C(a, b) \cdot \prod_{f \in V} \left[\frac{1 - d_f(a, b)}{1 - C(a, b)} \right] \quad (11)$$

226 where V is the set of criteria for which $d_f(a, b) > C(a, b)$. All the values
 227 $S(a, b)$ for each pair of alternatives provides the credibility matrix, from
 228 where the preference relation ‘ a is preferred over b ’, aPb , is expressed by
 229 combining $S(a, b)$ and $S(b, a)$ given a cut-off level λ .

230 The exploitation procedure consists of ascending and descending distilla-
 231 tion procedures that lead to two transitive pre-order, whose intersection
 232 generates the final ranking. These distillations are based on qualification
 233 scores of alternatives:

$$Score(a) = \#\{b|aPb\} - \#\{b|bPa\} \quad (12)$$

234 The descending distillation procedure extract the best alternative(s) ac-
 235 cording to these scores, then it repeats the same process with the remain-
 236 ing alternatives but decreasing the cutoff level λ (so it becomes easier for
 237 alternatives to be preferred) until remaining alternatives have the same
 238 scores. The ascending distillation procedure is similar, but extracting the
 239 worst alternative(s). The final partial pre-order O is defined as the inter-
 240 section of descending pre-order O_1 and ascending pre-order O_2 .

241 • **Multiplicative Multi-Objective Optimization by Ration Analysis**
 242 **(MultiMOORA)** (Brauers & Zavadskas, 2010). This method starts with
 243 a decision matrix showing the performance of different alternatives with
 244 respect to various attributes (objectives), and uses three ranking systems
 245 that are then combined. First, a ratio system is developed in which each
 246 performance of an alternative w.r.t each criterion is normalized as in Equa-
 247 tion 8 and then all the criteria for each alternative are aggregated as:

$$y_s^* = \sum_{f \in F^{max}} w_f \cdot r_{sf} - \sum_{f \in F^{min}} w_f \cdot r_{sf} \quad (13)$$

248 where F^{max} and F^{min} are the criteria to be maximized and minimized,
 249 respectively. With this, the alternatives are ranked in descending order of
 250 y_s^* values, resulting in the ratio system ranking.

251 Secondly, a reference point is computed as the best values of the normal-
 252 ized performance of alternatives w.r.t. each criterion:

$$r_f = \begin{cases} \max_{s' \in S} r_{s'f} & \text{if } f \in F^{max} \\ \min_{s' \in S} r_{s'f} & \text{if } f \in F^{min} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

253 The distance between each normalized alternative and this reference point
 254 are measured using Tchebycheff Min-Max metric:

$$\min_{s \in S} \left\{ \max_{f \in F} |w_f \cdot r_f - w_f \cdot r_{sf}| \right\} \quad (15)$$

255 Through this metric, the reference point system ranking is obtained.

256 The third ranking system consists of a full multiplicative form, where the
257 utility of an alternative s is given by:

$$U_s = \frac{A_s}{B_s} = \frac{\prod_{f \in F^{max}} v_f(s)}{\prod_{f \in F^{min}} v_f(s)} \quad (16)$$

258 Finally, these three ranking are combined based on dominance theory (Brauers
259 & Zavadskas, 2014) to get the final ranking for MultiMOORA.

260 • **Reference Ideal Method (RIM)** (Cables et al., 2016). This method
261 evolves a value or set of values (the reference ideal), that is always main-
262 tained between a maximum value and a minimum value. This method is
263 characterized to be independent of the type of data, and does not present
264 rank reversal, an aspect that is not present in other MCDM. RIM requires
265 for each criterion the range $[A, B]$ that belongs to a universe of discourse
266 and the reference ideal $[C, D]$ that represents the maximum importance or
267 relevance in a given range. The normalization based on these parameters
268 is computed as:

$$y_{sf} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } v_f(s) \in [C, D] \\ 1 - \frac{\min(|v_f(s)-C|, |v_f(s)-D|)}{|A-C|} & \text{if } v_f(s) \in [A, C] \wedge A \neq C \\ 1 - \frac{\min(|v_f(s)-C|, |v_f(s)-D|)}{|D-B|} & \text{if } v_f(s) \in [D, B] \wedge D \neq B \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

269 Then, the weighted normalized values $y'_{sf} = w_f \cdot y_{sf}$ are used to calculate
270 the variation to the normalized reference ideal (and anti-ideal) for each
271 alternative:

$$I_s^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{f \in F} (y'_{sf} - w_f)^2} \quad (18)$$

$$I_s^- = \sqrt{\sum_{f \in F} (y'_{sf})^2} \quad (19)$$

272 Finally, the relative index R_s of each alternative is computed using these
273 values and Equation 10, similarly as in TOPSIS. The alternatives are
274 ranked in descending order according to their relative index.

275 • **Weighted Aggregated Sum Product ASsessment (WASPAS)** (Zavad-
276 skas et al., 2012). It is an aggregation method that applies a joint criterion
277 based on the additive relative importance (computed using WSM) and the
278 multiplicative relative importance (computed using WPM), supposing the

279 increase of ranking accuracy and, respectively, the effectiveness of decision
 280 making. The method performs a normalization similar to ideal normaliza-
 281 tion in TOPSIS (Equation 9). The joint generalized criterion Q_s is then
 282 computed as:

$$Q_s = \lambda \sum_{f \in F} w_f \cdot r_{sf} + (1 - \lambda) \prod_{f \in F} (r_{sf})^{w_f} \quad (20)$$

283 where λ indicates the trade-off between the models (usually $\lambda = 0.5$).
 284 These joint generalized criterion values are ranked in a descending order,
 285 and the highest amount of joint generalized criterion has the highest rank.

286 2.1. Fuzzy MCDM

287 Sometimes, the preferences provided by the decision makers are not smooth,
 288 as the weights of the criteria could be expressed according to their importance
 289 using some linguistic term (e.g. low, medium, high). As these linguistic terms
 290 define a fuzzy degree of importance, they could be expressed as fuzzy numbers,
 291 and new fuzzy versions of the MCDM methods must be employed to consider
 292 them.

293 Designing ranking for each option is difficult for a decision maker under
 294 operational conditions, but fuzzy methods enable a decision maker to use fuzzy
 295 numbers in place of accurate ones. One of the most common fuzzy numbers are
 296 Triangular Fuzzy Numbers (TFNs) (Borovička, 2014), which are useful to handle
 297 imprecise numerical quantities. A TFN can be defined as a triplet (a_1, a_2, a_3) ,
 298 where a_2 is the value of maximum membership to the fuzzy set (i.e. most
 299 promising value) and a_1 and a_3 are the limits of membership to the fuzzy set
 300 (i.e. smallest and largest possible values).

301 In order to convert the linguistic terms to TFNs, a conversion scale is used
 302 (see Figure 1), where both the performance score and membership function μ_A
 303 are in the range $[0, 1]$. The value 0 means that the element is not a member of
 304 the fuzzy set, while the value 1 means that the element is fully a member of the
 305 fuzzy set. Values between 0 and 1 characterize fuzzy members, which belong to
 306 the fuzzy set only partially.

307 Algebra operations on TFN are similar to tuple operations for the sum and
 308 multiplication of TFNs, as well as the multiplication of a constant crisp number
 309 with a TFN. But in the case of subtraction and division, these operations for
 310 TFNs $\tilde{a} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ and $\tilde{b} = (b_1, b_2, b_3)$ are defined as follows:

$$\tilde{a} \ominus \tilde{b} = (a_1 - b_3, a_2 - b_2, a_3 - b_1) \quad (21)$$

$$\tilde{a} \oslash \tilde{b} = \left(\frac{a_1}{b_3}, \frac{a_2}{b_2}, \frac{a_3}{b_1} \right) \quad (22)$$

311 On the other hand, the distance between two TFN can be computed using
 312 the vertex method:

Figure 1: Linguistic scales and fuzzy weights numbers adopted.

$$d(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3}[(a_1 - b_1)^2 + (a_2 - b_2)^2 + (a_3 - b_3)^2]} \quad (23)$$

313 There exist some fuzzy versions of MCDM methods that deal with TFNs,
 314 including:

- 315 • **Fuzzy AHP** (Krejčí et al., 2017). In this fuzzy version, pairwise compar-
 316 isons are now expressed using linguistic variables (specified by TFNs). As
 317 in AHP, comparisons are converted into (fuzzy) numerical weights. In this
 318 case, the fuzzy version of the geometric mean is easier to apply than the
 319 Fuzzy Eigenvalue method. Given the TFN values $\tilde{a}_{ij} = (a_{ij1}, a_{ij2}, a_{ij3})$ in
 320 matrix A of size $p \times p$, the weights $\tilde{w}_i = (w_{i1}, w_{i2}, w_{i3})$ can be computed
 321 as:

$$w_{i1} = \frac{\sqrt[p]{\prod_{j=1}^p a_{ij1}}}{\sum_{k=1}^p \sqrt[p]{\prod_{j=1}^p a_{kj3}}} \quad (24)$$

$$w_{i2} = \frac{\sqrt[p]{\prod_{j=1}^p a_{ij2}}}{\sum_{k=1}^p \sqrt[p]{\prod_{j=1}^p a_{kj2}}} \quad (25)$$

$$w_{i3} = \frac{\sqrt[p]{\prod_{j=1}^p a_{ij3}}}{\sum_{k=1}^p \sqrt[p]{\prod_{j=1}^p a_{kj1}}} \quad (26)$$

322 Then, (fuzzy) numerical priorities are computed similarly to AHP using
 323 TFN algebra operations. Finally, to rank these TFNs, different fuzzy
 324 number comparators can be used, such as Chen method (Chen, 1985),
 325 which is used in this work.

326 • **Fuzzy VIKOR** (Opricovic, 2011). This fuzzy extension uses the same
 327 methods as in classic VIKOR for the computation of weighted and nor-
 328 malized Manhattan \tilde{S}_s and Chebyshev \tilde{R}_s distances based on the best
 329 $\tilde{f}^* = (f_1^*, f_2^*, f_3^*)$ and worst $\tilde{f}^- = (f_1^-, f_2^-, f_3^-)$ value for each criterion
 330 $f \in F$. For this fuzzy version, when performing operations with fuzzy
 331 numbers, Equations 5 and 6 must take into account the normalized fuzzy
 332 difference:

$$\tilde{d}_f(\tilde{s}) = \left(\frac{f_1^* - v_f(s)_3}{f_3^* - f_1^-}, \frac{f_2^* - v_f(s)_2}{f_3^* - f_1^-}, \frac{f_3^* - v_f(s)_1}{f_3^* - f_1^-} \right) \quad (27)$$

333 Similarly, when computing the maximum group utility \tilde{Q}_s , the denomina-
 334 tors become the difference between the largest value of the best and the
 335 smallest value of the worst; while numerators must consider consistently
 336 any fuzzy subtraction as stated in Equation 21. Finally, TFNs are de-
 337 fuzzified using the method ‘2nd weighted mean’, where a crisp value for
 338 the TFN is approximated as:

$$c(a) = \frac{a_1 + 2a_2 + a_3}{4} \quad (28)$$

339 and these crisp values are used as scores for ranking the same way as in
 340 VIKOR.

341 • **Fuzzy TOPSIS** (Chen, 2000). The extension of TOPSIS for TFN per-
 342 forms vectorial normalization as in Equation 8 taking into account the
 343 fuzzy operations. In the case of linear normalization, Equation 9 is ex-
 344 tended for fuzzy numbers, and in this case the maximum operator returns
 345 the largest value of the TFN (i.e. a_3) and the minimum operator returns
 346 the smallest value of the TFN (i.e. a_1). Fuzzy ideal and anti-ideal points
 347 can be constructed by defining fuzzy numbers $v_f^* = (1, 1, 1)$ and $v_f^- = (0, 0, 0)$
 348 for each criterion, respectively, and the distances of solutions to these ideal
 349 d_s^+ and anti-ideal d_s^- points are computed using the fuzzy distance pro-
 350 vided in Equation 23. With this, a crisp value is obtained, and so closeness
 351 ratio can be applied to get the ranking of solutions.

352 • **Fuzzy MultiMOORA** (Balezentis & Balezentis, 2013). In this fuzzy
 353 extension, each of the three ranking methods is converted into its fuzzy
 354 version by considering TFN and fuzzy operations. In the ratio system,
 355 fuzzy distance from Equation 23 is used in the normalization of the per-
 356 formance of alternatives w.r.t. each criterion, and the obtained results
 357 after applying this method are defuzzified using the best nonfuzzy perfor-
 358 mance (BNP) value:

$$BNP(a) = \frac{(a_3 - a_1) + (a_2 - a_1)}{3} + a_1 \quad (29)$$

359 For the reference point method, fuzzy distance is used to measure the
 360 distance of each solution to the ideal point, and the resulting crisp values
 361 are then used in the Tchebycheff Min-Max metric to obtain the reference
 362 point ranking. The fully multiplicative form follows Equation 16 consider-
 363 ing fuzzy operations, and then the fuzzy numbers \tilde{U}_s are defuzzified using
 364 BNP. Finally, these three ranking are combined using dominance theory
 365 as in classic MultiMOORA.

366 • **Fuzzy WASPAS** (Turskis et al., 2015). The extension of WASPAS for
 367 supporting fuzzy numbers is straightforward by considering fuzzy opera-
 368 tions in the WSM and WPM formulas. It must be noticed here, that the
 369 exponentiation operation of TFNs $\tilde{v} = v_1, v_2, v_3$ and $\tilde{w} = w_1, w_2, w_3$ for
 370 WPM is computed as follows:

$$\tilde{v}^{\tilde{w}} = (v_1^{w_3}, v_2^{w_2}, v_3^{w_1}) \quad (30)$$

371 Then, the TFNs obtained for WSM and WPM are defuzzified using the
 372 centroid method:

$$c(a) = \frac{a_1 + a_2 + a_3}{3} \quad (31)$$

373 and the rest of the method is applied with the obtained crisp numbers.

374 3. A DSS for Mission Plan Selection

375 The MCMPP considered in this work has been defined in previous works (Ramirez-
 376 Atencia & Camacho, 2018a) as a T-sized set of *tasks* $\mathcal{T} \doteq \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_T\}$ to
 377 be performed by a swarm of U UAVs $\mathcal{U} = \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_U\}$ within a specific
 378 time interval. In addition, G GCSs $\mathcal{G} \doteq \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_G\}$ control the swarm of
 379 UAVs. A mission plan consists of a tuple composed of the assignments of tasks
 380 to UAVs, the orders in which these tasks are performed (that can be represented
 381 as a permutation of orders), the assignments of UAVs to the GCSs controlling
 382 them, the assignment of sensors that the UAVs use at each task they perform,
 383 and the assignments of the flight profiles used by the UAVs in their path to each
 384 task they perform and in their return to the base.

385 An example of these plans can be seen in Figure 2, where there are 5 tasks, 3
 386 UAVs and 2 GCSs. Some tasks are assigned to several UAVs, which divide the
 387 task performance between them, like occurs in tasks 1, 3 and 4. In this example,
 388 two types of flight profile are considered: a minimum consumption profile (min)
 389 and a maximum speed profile (max). On the other hand, different sensors can be
 390 used to perform the tasks, including maritime radars (mR), synthetic aperture
 391 radars (sR), inverse synthetic aperture radars (iR) or electro-optical or infrared
 392 sensors (eiS).

393 When solving a MCMPP, there exists several constraints that must be
 394 checked at each solution in order to assure if they are valid, including fuel

1					2					3			4					5					6		
UAV					Order					GCS			FpPath					SensUsed					FpReturn		
T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	U ₁	U ₂	U ₃	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	U ₁	U ₂	U ₃
1	2	2	1	1	1	0	4	2	3	1	2	1	min	max	max	min	min	mR	vS	iR	mR	eiS	min	min	max
2		3	2										min		min	max		iR		sR	iR				
3			3										max		max			sR			sR				

Figure 2: Representation of the assignments that compose a mission plan.

395 constraints, time dependencies, path constraints, sensor constraints, GCS con-
396 straints, distance to ground and between UAVs, etc. All these constraints have
397 been detailed in previous works (Ramirez-Atencia & Camacho, 2018a; Ramirez-
398 Atencia et al., 2018a).

399 All of these constraints are defined using a CSP representation, which is then
400 used in the corresponding algorithm to check the consistency and correctness of
401 the solutions generated. In previous approaches (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2017a),
402 a MOEA algorithm was used to look for the solutions of this problem.

403 In this approach, after the solutions have been found, they are treated by
404 the DSS. In this context, the decision making process consists of selecting the
405 best plan for the mission among the plans returned by the mission planner. To
406 do that, the DSS consist of two modules: ranking and filtering.

407 The ranking module sorts the plans returned by the algorithm so the first
408 one should be the best according to the criteria considered, but the rest are also
409 returned to the user so he/she can take the final decision. The filtering module,
410 on the other hand, reduces the number of solutions returned by omitting similar
411 solutions.

412 To present these solutions to the operator, in order to allow the selection of
413 the best one, a Human-Machine Interface (HMI) was developed in a previous
414 work (Ramirez-Atencia & Camacho, 2018b), so the ordered and filtered solutions
415 are returned in a table indicating the values obtained for each criteria, and then a
416 graphical representation of each of the plans can be visualized in a GIS interface.

417 3.1. Mission Planning solutions through Multi-Objective Optimization

418 In previous works (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2017a), the MCMPP was solved
419 using a MOEA; concretely, an extension of Non-dominated Sorting Genetic
420 Algorithm-II (NSGA-II) (Deb et al., 2002) that use the CSP model inside the
421 fitness function in order to check if the solutions are valid.

422 In addition, when solutions are valid, this algorithm considers the multiple
423 optimization objectives of the problem in order to select the fittest solutions that
424 are inside the POF. The optimization objectives considered in this problem are
425 the total cost of the mission, the end time of the mission or makespan, the total
426 fuel consumption, the total flight time, the total distance traversed, the risk of
427 the mission and the number of UAVs used in the mission.

428 With the high number of optimization objectives considered, the number of
429 optimal solutions of the POF becomes huge. As at some point the operator
430 will have to select a concrete plan to be executed, getting so many solutions
431 will highly increase the decision making process. Moreover, some of these non-
432 dominated solutions may not be optimal enough, e.g. a little improvement in
433 some objectives may suppose a big lost in the rest of objectives.

434 To get rid of this problem, the approach focuses the search on knee points,
435 so only a limited set of the most significant solutions are returned, and not
436 the entire POF as other MOEAs usually do. This approach changes the concept
437 of domination, used by NSGA-II to guide the search towards the POF,
438 to conedomination, which focus the search on knee points using a specific cone
439 angle that increase the number of solutions that are dominated by a concrete
440 one. With this the number of solutions is highly reduced while the decrease of
441 hypervolume (measuring the quality of the POF) is not very high.

442 With this, the DSS will receive only the most significant solutions, so the
443 decision making process will be easier for the operator.

444 3.2. Ranking system

445 Once the set of plans is obtained, it is necessary to rank them before they
446 are presented to the operator in order to ease the selection process, assuring
447 that most times the final solution selected by the operator is the first in this
448 ranking. In order to do that, several criteria are considered:

- 449 1. The **makespan**, i.e. the end time of the mission. We have computed it as
450 the maximum of the return times of the UAVs, which must be minimized.
- 451 2. The **total cost** of the mission, an objective that must always be mini-
452 mized. To compute it, it is necessary to sum the cost of each UAV usage,
453 which is computed as the flight time of each UAV multiplied by the cost
454 per hour of the UAV.
- 455 3. The **total fuel consumed**, i.e the sum of the fuel consumed by each UAV
456 at performing the tasks of the mission. This is the main objective in most
457 UAV mission planning problems that we need to minimize.
- 458 4. The **total distance traversed**, i.e the sum of the distances traversed by
459 each UAV at performing the tasks of the mission. In most UAV mission
460 planning problems, this objective is minimized.
- 461 5. The **total flight time**, i.e. the sum of the flight time of each UAV at
462 performing the tasks of the mission. We have computed it as the sum of
463 the flight times of all the UAVs, which must be minimized.
- 464 6. The **risk factor for the maximum Percentage of Fuel Usage per**
465 **UAV**. It is computed as the maximum of the fuel consumed divided by
466 the initial fuel for all UAVs, which must be minimized.

- 467 7. The **risk factor for the minimum distance to the ground**, i.e. the
468 minimum of the minimum distances to the ground of each UAV at perform-
469 ing the tasks of the mission. A percentage indicating the risk is computed
470 with a given risk value, which indicates the maximum risky altitude to
471 the ground. This objective is usually minimized.
- 472 8. The **risk factor for the minimum between UAVs**, i.e. the minimum
473 of the minimum distances between each pair of UAVs at performing the
474 mission. A percentage indicating the risk is computed with a given risk
475 value, which indicates the maximum risky distance between UAVs. This
476 objective is usually minimized.
- 477 9. The **risk factor for the time when UAV leave GCSs coverage**
478 **zones**. It is computed as the maximum sum of durations in which a UAV
479 is not covered by the GCS, and using a given risk value, a percentage is
480 obtained as in the previous risk factors. This variable must be minimized.
- 481 10. The **number of UAVs used** in the mission. A mission performed with a
482 lower number of vehicles is usually better because the remaining vehicles
483 can perform other missions at the same time. Therefore, this objective
484 must be minimized.
- 485 11. The **number of GCSs used** in the mission. When we have a Multi-GCS
486 mission, using a lower number of GCSs is usually better in order to use as
487 less resources as possible. Therefore, this objective must be minimized.

488 In this work, the preferences of the operator define the weights of the criteria
489 needed in the ranking algorithm. This leads to the definition of operator profiles,
490 where each criterion is ranked in degrees of importance, expressed using the
491 following linguistic terms: *Very low (1)*, *Low (2)*, *Medium (3)*, *High (4)* and
492 *Very high (5)*.

493 These linguistic terms are often fuzzy, and thus, fuzzy weights are used.
494 In this work, TFNs(Borovička, 2014) are employed, which are useful to handle
495 imprecise numerical quantities. The membership function used to convert each
496 linguistic term to a TFN is presented in Table 1. Since in this membership
497 function the distance between numbers is too big and the logical values obtained
498 from the table are critical for the decision maker, it can be said that it is a
499 beginning for all calculations.

500 With this, a fuzzy MCDM method can be used taking these TFNs as weights.
501 This algorithm will be applied to the solutions obtained by the MOEA, which
502 have crisp values. The resultant ordered solutions are then passed to the filtering
503 system.

504 3.3. Filtering system

505 Even though a ranked set of solutions is presented, often the operator will
506 check these solutions. In this case, he/she may be overwhelmed if there is a
507 high number of solutions. The filtering of the solutions is performed in order

Table 1: Transformation of linguistic scales for fuzzy membership functions.

Linguistic scale (Rank)	TFN Membership function
Very low	(0.00, 0.10, 0.25)
Low	(0.15, 0.30, 0.45)
Medium	(0.35, 0.5, 0.65)
High	(0.55, 0.70, 0.85)
Very high	(0.75, 0.90, 1.00)

508 to remove very similar solutions from the final list presented to the operator.
 509 Although the knee-point based MOEA presented in section 3.1 already returns a
 510 reduced list of solutions, it only looks for similar solutions in terms of optimality,
 511 while this filtering system focuses on the similarity of plans, i.e. how similar the
 512 assignments are.

513 In order to know the similarity of the solutions, a distance function has been
 514 designed. This distance function computes the proximity between two solutions
 515 by counting the different values for each variable of the solution, as shown in
 516 Figure 3, where the different values in the solution below are represented in
 517 gray. In this example, $\Delta_{uav}(s_1, s_2) = 1$, as the only difference is that UAV 1 is
 518 not performing task T_4 . Nevertheless, $\Delta_{path}(s_1, s_2) = 2$, as flight profiles in the
 519 paths for tasks T_2 and T_4 changed.

Figure 3: Representation of two similar solutions and the filtering values used when applying the distance function

520 The filter distance function needs to define a set of filtering weights for each
 521 variable, which should be given according to the degree of importance of that
 522 variable. According to Airbus Defence and Space expert operators, the less
 523 important variables are those related with flight profiles (w_{path} and w_{return})
 524 and sensors used (w_{sensor}), so they should be given a low value (e.g. 0.1), while
 525 task assignments (w_{uav}) are the most important variables when differentiating
 526 two solutions, so they should be given a high value (e.g. 1.0). To complete the

527 example, Order variables can be given a filtering value of $w_{order} = 0.6$ and GCS
 528 variables, not so important, a filtering value of $w_{gcs} = 0.2$.

529 So, once we got for each variable the Δ values, as shown in Figure 3, we can
 530 compute the planning distance d_{plan} between two solutions as:

$$d_{plan}(s_1, s_2) = w_{uav} \cdot \Delta_{uav}(s_1, s_2) + w_{order} \cdot \Delta_{order}(s_1, s_2) + w_{gcs} \cdot \Delta_{gcs}(s_1, s_2) + w_{path} \cdot \Delta_{path}(s_1, s_2) + w_{return} \cdot \Delta_{return}(s_1, s_2) + w_{sensor} \cdot \Delta_{sensor}(s_1, s_2) \quad (32)$$

531 Then, a threshold value is used to decide when two solutions are too similar
 532 and one of them must be removed from the set of solutions. The removed solu-
 533 tion will be the one with the lowest ranking value. The selection of the threshold
 534 value must provide the biggest deletion of similar solutions but maintaining the
 535 quality of the POF.

536 4. Experiments

537 In order to evaluate the proposed DSS, both its ranking and filtering sys-
 538 tems, 12 missions of increasing complexity were applied the knee-point based
 539 MOEA developed in a previous work (Ramirez-Atencia et al., 2017a), and dif-
 540 ferent solutions were obtained. Table 2 presents the complexity factors of these
 541 missions and the number of solutions obtained.

Table 2: Features of the different datasets designed.

Dataset Id.	Tasks	Multi-UAV Tasks	UAVs	GCSs	Number of Solutions
1	6	1	3	1	17
2	6	1	4	2	5
3	8	2	5	2	38
4	9	2	5	2	9
5	9	2	6	2	5
6	10	2	6	2	18
7	11	3	6	2	3
8	12	3	7	3	11
9	12	3	8	3	5
10	13	4	7	3	4
11	14	4	8	3	5
12	16	5	10	3	8

542 Then, in order to select the best MCDM method for ranking, 6 fuzzy MCDM
 543 methods were considered: Fuzzy AHP, Fuzzy VIKOR, Fuzzy TOPSIS (where
 544 two versions based on different normalisation procedures are considered: Fuzzy

545 TOPSISVector, using the vector normalisation, and Fuzzy TOPSISLinear, using
546 the linear transformation of maximum), Fuzzy MultiMOORA and Fuzzy
547 WASPAS. In addition, 10 classical MCDM methods were also considered in the
548 comparison: WSM, WPM, AHP, VIKOR, TOPSIS (both TOPSISVector and
549 TOPSISLinear), ELECTRE III, MultiMOORA, RIM and WASPAS.

550 In these methods, the linguistic scale presented in section 3.2 is used with
551 the fuzzy set transformation of Table 1 for the fuzzy MCDM methods. But
552 for classical MCDM methods, these linguistic terms are converted into numeric
553 weights. So the weights can be expressed as a percentage factor, so for each
554 criteria factor $f \in F$, given its degree of importance $D_I(f) \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$, its
555 corresponding weight is computed as:

$$w(f) = \frac{D_I(f)}{\sum_{f' \in F} D_I(f')} \quad (33)$$

556 In the case of AHP, the pairwise comparison matrix of criteria is constructed
557 based on the different scales for each criterion on the operator profile. Each pair-
558 wise value for $f, f' \in F$ is $D_I(f)/D_I(f')$. Similarly, for the pairwise comparison
559 matrix of alternatives w.r.t a given criterion, the performance values v_f for each
560 pair of alternatives $s, s' \in S$ are converted into a 1-9 scale based on the min-
561 imum and maximum values of that criteria (obtained in the MOEA). In the
562 fuzzy case, both weights and alternatives pairwise comparisons are transformed
563 into TFNs. This does not apply when two alternatives have the same value,
564 where the crisp number will be used instead.

565 For ELECTRE III, the indifferent, preference and veto threshold were defined
566 by expert operators. These values are presented in Table 3. In RIM, the
567 range $[A, B]$ for each criterion is set to the minimum and maximum values ob-
568 tained in the MOEA, while the reference ideal $[C, D]$ is set to the best values
569 obtained for each criterion in an interval with the indifference threshold. For
570 the rest of parameters, we define $v = 0.5$ in VIKOR and $\lambda = 0.5$ in WASPAS.

Table 3: Indifferent (q), Preference (p) and Veto (v) Thresholds for ELECTRE III used in this experiment.

	q	p	v
Cost	0.5	5.0	50.0
Distance (km)	0.5	5.0	50.0
Flight Time (h)	0.01	0.5	1.5
Fuel (kg)	0.5	7.0	50.0
Makespan (h)	0.005	0.3	1.0
Num GCSs	0	1	2
Num UAVs	0	1	4
Risk Distance Ground (%)	0.001	0.1	0.5
Risk Distance UAVs (%)	0.001	0.1	0.5
Risk Fuel Usage (%)	0.001	0.1	0.5
Risk Out of Coverage (%)	0.001	0.1	0.5

571 In addition, six operator profiles were created considering different impor-
572 tance degrees on each optimization criterion (very low, low, medium, high, very
573 high). These profiles are shown in Table 4. Then, these values are used as
574 weights through the aforementioned transformations.

Table 4: Operator Profiles used in this experiment.

	Balanced	Cost	Time	Risk	Resources	RiskCost
Cost	Medium	Very High	Medium	Low	High	Very High
Distance	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium
Flight Time	Medium	Low	High	Medium	Low	Low
Fuel	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	High	High
Makespan	Medium	Low	Very High	Medium	Low	Low
Num GCSs	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	Very High	Medium
Num UAVs	Medium	High	Medium	High	Very High	High
Risk Distance Ground	Medium	Medium	Low	Very High	Medium	Very High
Risk Distance UAVs	Medium	Medium	Low	Very High	Medium	Very High
Risk Fuel Usage	Medium	Medium	Low	Very High	Medium	Very High
Risk Out of Coverage	Medium	Low	Low	Very High	Medium	Very High

575 4.1. Evaluation Criteria

576 In order to perform an external evaluation of the quality of a ranking, and
577 to compare different ranking systems objectively, we have created a “ground
578 truth” dataset based on collective human judgement. Human judgement as a
579 way to create ground truth data is a common approach used in many domains
580 such as image recognition or performance analysis (Rodríguez-Fernández et al.,
581 2017).

582 In this work, the evaluation (or ground truth) data is created by asking 4
583 expert UAV operators to decide, given a set of unranked mission plans of the
584 same scenario and a concrete operator profile, which of them is the best, i.e.,
585 which of them they would choose to be executed in a real environment. For
586 each decision submitted by the operator, the following data is saved:

- 587 • The operator profile.
- 588 • An identifier of the mission scenario being evaluated.
- 589 • An identifier of the chosen plan.

590 The process of gathering human judgement-based evaluation data has been
591 automated by the use of a web-app, whose graphical user interface can be seen
592 in Figure 4. The use of this app can be summarised in three iterative steps:

- 593 1. The operator selects an operator profile. These profiles taking part of the
594 evaluation process must be loaded beforehand.
- 595 2. For each mission scenario to evaluate, a table with several possible solu-
596 tions (plans) is displayed, one per row. Each column shows the value of a
597 specific risk factor. To allow an easier comparison between the solutions,

Figure 4: Screenshot of the app developed to retrieve the evaluation data.

598 each cell is shaded with a two-coloured progress bar. The green part of
 599 the bar represents the relative quality of the risk factor with respect to
 600 the rest of solutions in the table. The red part is only used to fill the rest of
 601 the cell. As an example, the solution(s) with the minimum makespan in
 602 the table will display the corresponding makespan cell with a fully green
 603 shade. On the contrary, the solution(s) that maximizes the makespan will
 604 be fully red. In addition to the table, the operator may also select any of
 605 the solutions to visually inspect the plan in the mission map (See Figure
 606 4).

607 3. The operator judges which is the best plan by selecting it on the table
 608 and clicking the “Save decision” button. The app will automatically restart
 609 the decision process with a new mission.

With the evaluation dataset created, we can give a score to the rankings
 created by a MCDM algorithm in the context of this work. The score is aimed
 to assess whether the best plan selected by the operator is found within the
 top results of the algorithm or not. Let a be a MCDM algorithm, m a mission
 scenario and op an operator profile, then $L(a, m, op)$ denotes the ordered list of
 solutions (plans) returned by the algorithm in that context. Having an ordered

list L , $r(L, p)$ denotes the rank position of plan p in the list L , where 1 means “best”. On the other hand, let op be an operator profile, we refer to $S_{dm}(op, m)$ as the selection of best plan made by the operator or decision maker dm for the profile op in the context of mission m . This selection is retrieved from the evaluation dataset. With all this, we can define the *score* of an algorithm for a given operator profile and a given mission scenario as follows:

$$Score_{dm}(a, op, m) = \frac{\text{num_solutions}(m) - r(L(a, m, op), S_{dm}(op, m))}{\text{num_solutions}(m) - 1}, \quad (34)$$

610 As it can be seen, the value of the score is bounded on $[0, 1]$, where 1 repre-
 611 sents the best possible matching (the selected plan is the first of the algorithm
 612 ranking) and 0 the worst (the selected plan is the last of the algorithm ranking).
 613 Then, the final score is computed as the average of scores obtained for each op-
 614 erator. In order to give a general score for an algorithm, we take the average
 615 value of Eq. 34 over every operator, profile and mission scenario available in
 616 the evaluation dataset.

617 4.2. Comparing MCDM methods for the ranking system

618 Now, the different MCDM and fuzzy MCDM methods for the ranking system
 619 are compared in order to find the best one for the mission plan selection. The
 620 experiments have been performed in three steps:

- 621 1. Each algorithm has been executed for every mission with the different
 622 operator profiles as weights of the optimization criteria.
- 623 2. The operators have selected the best plan using an evaluation app.
- 624 3. The score metric is applied to every tuple (operator, mission, profile, algorithm)
 625 obtained after finishing the previous steps.

626 In order to give a global score for an algorithm, we take the average value of
 627 Equation 34 over every mission scenario available in the evaluation dataset and
 628 every operator profile. With these results, in order to compare if fuzzy MCDM
 629 methods are better than classical MCDM methods, Table 5 shows the difference
 630 between the average scores obtained for each pair of fuzzy and non-fuzzy MCDM
 631 method.

632 In this table, each column represents the difference of score between the
 633 fuzzy MCDM method of that column and the MCDM method of each row. It
 634 is clearly appreciable that there are more positive differences, which means that
 635 fuzzy methods obtained in general better results than non-fuzzy methods. On
 636 the other hand, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to check the statistical
 637 significance of these results, where the underlined values obtained a p-value less
 638 than 0.05 for that pair of algorithms. In general, it can be appreciate that fuzzy
 639 MCDM methods are statistically significant with respect to MCDM methods.
 640 So, it can be inferred that fuzzy MCDM methods are more appropriate to deal
 641 with this kind of problem.

Table 5: Comparison between classical and Fuzzy MCDM methods in the context of ranking solutions of a multi-UAV mission planning problem. Cells represent the difference in the average score between fuzzy methods (columns) and classical methods (rows). Underlined cells indicate that the difference is statistically significant (p-value < 0.05).

	Fuzzy AHP	Fuzzy VIKOR	Fuzzy TOPSISLinear	Fuzzy TOPSISVector	Fuzzy MultiMOORA	Fuzzy WASPAS
WSM	<u>0.042</u>	<u>0.166</u>	<u>0.097</u>	0.033	<u>0.073</u>	<u>0.092</u>
WPM	-0.03	<u>0.094</u>	<u>0.025</u>	<u>-0.039</u>	0.001	0.02
AHP	-0.021	<u>0.103</u>	<u>0.035</u>	<u>-0.029</u>	0.011	<u>0.029</u>
VIKOR	<u>-0.116</u>	0.008	<u>-0.06</u>	<u>-0.125</u>	<u>-0.085</u>	<u>-0.066</u>
TOPSISLinear	-0.008	<u>0.116</u>	<u>0.047</u>	<u>-0.017</u>	0.023	<u>0.042</u>
TOPSISVector	0.032	<u>0.156</u>	<u>0.087</u>	<u>0.023</u>	<u>0.063</u>	<u>0.082</u>
ELECTRE	<u>0.042</u>	<u>0.167</u>	<u>0.098</u>	<u>0.034</u>	<u>0.074</u>	<u>0.093</u>
MultiMOORA	-0.036	<u>0.089</u>	<u>0.02</u>	<u>-0.044</u>	-0.004	0.014
RIM	<u>0.039</u>	<u>0.163</u>	<u>0.094</u>	0.03	<u>0.07</u>	<u>0.089</u>
WASPAS	<u>-0.045</u>	<u>0.079</u>	0.011	<u>-0.054</u>	-0.014	<u>0.005</u>

642 Now, focusing on the different Fuzzy MCDM methods, Figure 5 clearly shows
643 that Fuzzy VIKOR obtained the best results. This approach was validated as
644 the most suitable to apply in the context of this work. In order to check the
645 statistical significance of these results, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used
646 again, comparing Fuzzy VIKOR with the rest of fuzzy methods. The p-value
647 obtained was less than 0.05 for all of the algorithms. It is interesting that Fuzzy
648 AHP, although being a quite popular method, did not obtain so good results as
649 the rest. This is probably because the pairwise comparisons were constructed
650 from weights of criteria, and not directly provided by decision makers. As the
651 rest of methods are based on weights, it is not surprising that they obtain better
652 results for this kind of problem.

653 Now, in order to see if some operator profile was harder for the MCDM
654 methods, the median of the scores aggregated by operator profile are presented
655 in Figure 6. It is clearly appreciable that *Balanced* is the most difficult profile
656 to evaluate, followed by the *Time* profile. This could be due to the different
657 conception of what balance means to an expert operator and to an algorithm
658 based on fuzzy weights.

659 In conclusion, the ranking of solutions of the MCMPP can be done using
660 Fuzzy VIKOR, which obtained the best performance with the smallest variance
661 in the experimental results. An optimal result is obtained with most operator
662 profiles, except for balanced profiles, which are harder to solve for most MCDM
663 algorithms.

664 4.3. Tuning the threshold for the filtering system

665 In order to decide which is the best possible threshold value for the MCMPP,
666 the ranked plans obtained in the previous section were used. With this, we apply
667 the similarity function $d_{plan}(s_1, s_2)$ to each pair of solutions s_1 and s_2 .

668 Then, different threshold values from 0 to 5, with an increment of 0.1, are
669 tested, and the remaining solutions after the filtering using that threshold are
670 used to compute the hypervolume of these filtered sets. The results obtained

Figure 5: Average scores and standard deviation of the different Fuzzy MCDM algorithms applied to the plan selection for MPP.

671 are shown in Figure 7, where each plot represents a mission of the problem,
 672 the threshold is presented in the horizontal axis and the hypervolume and the
 673 number of remaining solutions are presented in the vertical axis. With this,
 674 it can be concluded that the best threshold value (for MCMPPs) to be used
 675 is 1 (see the red line in the figure), since missions 1 and 2 have a great loss of
 676 hypervolume for bigger values than 1. Looking at the rest of missions, this value
 677 could be bigger, e.g. 3, since the hypervolume does not highly decrease before
 678 this value, but neither does the number of solutions, which are pretty similar
 679 between threshold values of 1 and 3.

680 5. Conclusions and Future Work

681 In this work, a DSS for plan selection in the context of the MCMPP has
 682 been designed and tested. This DSS requires the solutions obtained by a mis-
 683 sion planner, and the operator profiles, which can be directly specified by the
 684 operators, where each criterion of the decision problem is given a degree of
 685 importance using a linguistic term.

686 The DSS presented is composed of two modules: the ranking module and
 687 the filtering module. In the first module, the solutions are ranked based on

Figure 6: Median scores for the different operator profiles used in the plan selection of the MPP.

688 the operator profiles using a fuzzy MCDM algorithm. Several fuzzy and non-
 689 fuzzy MCDM algorithms were tested with the solutions obtained in a previous
 690 work, and it was concluded that fuzzy methods got better results than non-fuzzy
 691 methods; and, for this problem, Fuzzy VIKOR was the fittest one.

692 On the other hand, the filtering module uses the ranked solutions returned
 693 by the ranking module and filters those which are more similar based on a
 694 distance function. This function compares each variable of the CSP model of
 695 the MCMPP, providing a specific weight depending on the importance of the
 696 variable. In order to decide the threshold value of the filtering function, different
 697 thresholds were tested, and it was concluded that the value 1 was the fittest value
 698 in terms of highest hypervolume and lowest number of remaining solutions.

699 This DSS highly decreases the operator workload since it facilitates the op-
 700 erator decision process, which is pretty hard when the number of solutions re-
 701 turned is large. In any case, although the operator is provided with the final list
 702 of ranked and filtered solutions, the final selection that must be eventually made,
 703 depends on his/her decision. For this, it is necessary to provide a well-designed
 704 environment that allows the operator to visualize the ranked alternatives and
 705 select the most appropriate. This is described in the following chapter.

706 In future works, it would be interesting to improve the system by considering
 707 the final selection made by the operators. Using this and some pattern recog-
 708 nition or machine learning techniques, the operator profile would be updated,
 709 aiming to perform better in future decisions. On the other hand, some machine
 710 learning technique could be used to automatize the threshold selection for the
 711 filtering system according to the plans obtained.

Figure 7: Hypervolume and number of remaining solutions after the similarity filtering with different threshold values. The red line marks the common threshold chosen as most suited for this experimentation after an empirical study.

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